

School Name:

Farzanegan High School (NODET - SAMPAD)

Research Title:

Using plant extracts as a **biological battery**

Researcher Name:

Melika Khadem

(This research has been conducted for the first time in the world)

Abstract:

Electricity, as the backbone of industrial development, social welfare, and technological progress, plays a crucial role in modern life. However, conventional methods of electricity generation, such as fossil fuel power plants and even some nuclear techniques, face significant challenges. Dependence on non-renewable resources, high extraction and transportation costs, large-scale greenhouse gas emissions and air pollutants, and direct impacts on climate change are among the major issues of these methods. Additionally, water consumption in power plants, ecosystem disruption, and economic instability due to fossil fuel price fluctuations emphasize the need for novel electricity generation approaches.

In contrast, green and renewable energy sources offer a more sustainable and cost-effective solution for electricity supply. A promising approach in this context is generating electricity from waste materials, which not only reduces waste volume and pollution but also provides a local and renewable energy source. This technology, by converting waste into energy, contributes to environmental preservation while promoting sustainable development and broader access to clean electricity.

In this study, I attempted to use plant peel waste and extract their bioactive compounds as a biological battery, proposing a novel method for electricity generation using green energy. The advantages of this research include material availability, low cost, avoidance of harmful chemicals, empowerment of communities, environmental benefits, and reduction of electricity consumption costs.

Research Topic: Using plant extracts as a biological battery

Keywords: Plant extracts, biological battery, green energy, clean electricity, plant peel waste

Introduction:

Humans have always sought comfort, illumination, security, and easy access to energy resources to improve their lives. Today, electricity is one of the most fundamental human needs, and its presence in daily life is so pervasive that its absence can disrupt normal activities. From home lighting and kitchen appliances to medical devices such as pacemakers, blood pressure monitors, and glucose meters, all rely on electrical energy. Even everyday communication through mobile phones, computers, and the internet is impossible without electricity. In fact, electricity acts as a hidden force, supporting human comfort, health, and safety in the smallest details of life.

Furthermore, electricity plays a crucial role in economic development and social welfare. Manufacturing industries, transportation, modern agriculture, and even financial services all depend on stable access to electrical energy. Electricity increases productivity, reduces production costs, promotes technological innovation, and ultimately enhances quality of life. The cleaner and more sustainable the energy sources, the greater the potential for environmental preservation alongside economic growth and social well-being.

However, conventional electricity generation, especially from fossil fuels, faces numerous challenges and disadvantages. This type of energy production releases greenhouse gases and air pollutants, exacerbating climate change and causing respiratory and other health problems. Additionally, fossil fuel resources are limited and increasingly difficult and costly to extract. Power plants and transmission lines may pose safety risks, accidents, or explosions, while their construction and operation can negatively affect ecosystems and biodiversity. Moreover, electricity production and distribution incur high costs, and some power plants generate noise and thermal pollution that reduce human quality of life.

Humans have long sought green and renewable energy as a sustainable alternative to conventional and polluting sources. However, challenges such as high costs, water scarcity, and the installation of solar panels and wind turbines remain significant obstacles. According to documented statistics, approximately 300 million tons of plant peel waste are discarded worldwide each year. These plant peels represent a valuable, low-cost resource for green energy production.

In this study, I aim to generate and compare electricity from plants and plant peel extracts using a fruit-powered clock, measuring the produced electric energy to identify the most effective method. The primary goal of this research is to measure the voltage generated by plants and plant peel extracts. For this experiment, water and five plant types (mandarin, apple, cantaloupe, pomegranate, and beetroot) were selected.

Plant Extracts: These are concentrated substances obtained from plants through pressing, soaking, boiling, distillation, or using specific solvents to isolate active compounds such as vitamins, antioxidants, or essential oils.

Fruit-Powered Clock: This device generates electricity by inserting two metal electrodes (copper and zinc) into a fruit, where chemical reactions between the fruit acids and metals produce an electric current sufficient to power a small clock or LED.

Green Energy: Energy produced from renewable natural sources with minimal environmental impact, including solar, wind, water, geothermal, and biomass energy, which, unlike fossil fuels, do not release greenhouse gases or pollutants.

Electricity: The flow or accumulation of electric charges that can produce energy for lighting, heating, motion, and the operation of various devices.

Plant Peel Waste: Parts of fruits, vegetables, and other plants that remain after harvesting, processing, or consumption and are generally discarded as waste.

Plant Extractor Device: A tool that isolates rich plant extracts and active compounds through pressure or extraction for use in medicinal, nutritional, or industrial applications.

Research background:

1-A study presented by a researcher from Hungary. It uses green and free energy from algae to illuminate the environment.

2- A watch that works with the blood of crabs. Researchers in the United States designed a biological cell that is capable of producing energy from sugars in the bloodstream of crabs. Energy-producing biological cells had previously been tested in rabbit ears, insect stomachs, snail and oyster body cavities. (In my opinion, the purpose of using green energy is to use nature properly and we should not destroy animals and insects and call it green energy)

Research method:

In this research, the experimental method has been used, which has an independent, dependent and control variable. In this research, we reach the real goal through experimentation.

Project Question: Can water and plant extracts act as biological batteries?

General objectives:

Production of bio-battery and electricity by plant extracts (apple, pomegranate, red pumpkin, tangerine, melon) with the help of fruit clock detection and plant extraction device

Sub-objectives:

Comparison and measurement of the voltage produced by plants and plant bark extracts and selection of a better source for electrical energy and production of biological-battery

Hypothesis:

I think plant extracts can produce more green energy than plants themselves.

Independent variable: Extracts and plants

Dependent variable: Voltage of electricity

Controlled variable:

Fruit clock (consisting of two pieces of copper and zinc)

Required materials and method:

- 1-Water
- 2-Two pieces of copper metal
- 3-Two pieces of zinc metal
- 4-Several pieces of wire in different colors
- 5-Several plant samples
- 6-Extraction device
- 7-Multimeter
- 8-Two glasses
- 9-Graduated cylinder
- 10-Small lidded jars for samples
- 11-Computer clock

To prepare the extract, pour the plant peels into a pot and use the extraction device to obtain the plant extract after an hour.

Then I filled them in two 50 ml glasses using a graduated cylinder and using a fruit clock and immersing the copper and zinc metals in the plant extract, I noticed that the clock started. So I measured the electrical current generated with a multimeter.

I also placed the plants themselves in the fruit clock and measured the electrical current generated with a multimeter.

Table:

plant	Amount of electrical energy produced in volts
Pomegranate	1.50
Red Pumpkin	1,86
Tangerine	1.44
Apple	1.80
cantaloupe	1.89
Water	1.52

explanation: Table of electrical energy production rates from plant extracts. The names of the plants are on the left and the voltage produced is on the right of the table.

plant	Amount of electrical energy produced in volts
Pomegranate	1.87
Red Pumpkin	1,76
Tangerine	1.39
Apple	1.88
cantaloupe	-

explanation: Table of electrical energy production rates of plants in volts. The names of the plants are on the left and the voltage levels are on the right of the table.

Chart:

the chart of the amount of electrical energy produced from plant extracts and water

Diagram of electrical energy produced from plants

Data Analysis:

According to the experiments and data review, the electrical energy produced by plant extracts is more than the electrical energy produced by the plant itself.

In the experiment of extracts, the extract of the skin of the cantaloupe plant produced the most electricity with 1.89 volts, and in the experiment of the plants themselves, the apple fruit produced the most electricity with 1.88 volts.

All plants and their extracts and water produced electrical energy except the cantaloupe plant. While the cantaloupe plant extract produced the most electricity, the fruit clock with the cantaloupe plant itself did not light up.

Conclusion:

The results of the experiment confirm my hypothesis because it shows that water and plant extracts can keep the desired clock on as a biological battery, and because plants and their skins lose their water after a while and dry out, or some may rot, therefore using plant extracts is more economical and has other applications. On the other hand, it prevents us from using batteries in this experiment, which have various environmental pollution effects.

Suggestions:

My research used plant extracts; after much searching, I found out that this experiment is being conducted for the first time in the world. Although this method may need further development to produce high-voltage energy, we can modify it to charge heart batteries, charge mine-detecting robots, measure blood sugar and blood pressure.

Maybe, in addition to the solar batteries that are placed on traffic lights on streets and roads, we can make a glass and connect it to the light, and when it rains or snows and the glass is full, the lights can also use the energy of water and stay on. Or we can grow plants inside these glasses that grow to a certain extent and use the energy in their soil to light the lights. Of course, they also create a beautiful view in the city and on the road.

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